
Mechanisms for Lending to Individuals through Foreign Credit Lines

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Abstract: The article analyzes the problems and current state of improving retail banking services in the process of digital transformation of banks. The results of this article provide practical suggestions and recommendations for the study of factors affecting the development of retail banking services and the elimination of problematic situations.

Key words: retail banking, retail lending, underwriter, residential income, mobile app.

Introduction

The digitalization of the economy and the number of key services of the economic system are also increasing day by day and becoming digital. The creation of opportunities for remote implementation of traditional banking services and the provision of services online has ushered in an era of providing services through new modern platforms for banks.

In such circumstances, the transformation of banking activities indicates an increase in efficiency and increased competition between banks through the automation and digitization of banking services. In order to effectively transform banks, it is necessary to be among the first to introduce innovative banking products and services in many respects and not be afraid to make sufficient investments in the sector.

When banks provide retail loans to individuals, the borrower's income is one of the main parameters taken into account by the bank when making a decision to grant a loan and determining the amount that can be allocated.

The study focuses on retail banking customers in Uzbekistan in two important aspects. The first is a mechanism for pre-selecting eligible customers from among those with a lower risk profile. The second is the bank's location in the most attractive location and segmenting customers to create a product that is suitable for them.

Although different industries have developed different strategies and approaches to selling their products, the importance of a personal approach in selling products remains high. Undoubtedly, a personal approach in selling products requires two-way communication, which, in the case of financial institutions, involves a personal approach aimed at taking appropriate measures to convince the other person [2]. The satisfaction after the sale of products cannot be ignored. It always serves as the basis for establishing long and profitable relationships [3].

To the topic related literature analysis

The issues of improving the efficiency of credit line management in commercial banks have been studied in scientific studies by a number of foreign scholars and the concept of a credit line has been expressed in the definitions given to its essence. For example, American economists Chris J. Barlton and Diana McNaughton define a credit line as a grouping of loans.

N. Sokolinskaya also defines a credit line as “a combination of short-term and long-term loans.” The focus of this definition on the term of the loan does not fully reveal the essence of the credit

line. Because the determination of the term of loans issued by the bank and its compliance with it can only be an important factor in determining the quality of the credit line.

The famous Russian economist OILavrushin defines "the concept of a credit line in banking is usually understood as the sum of loans from one or another bank." At the same time, he believes that the formation of a credit line in a bank and its analysis allow a commercial bank to clearly develop its strategy and tactics, increasing its ability to lend to customers.

Abalkin LI, Panova GS and a group of other economists believe that the credit portfolio of commercial banks is a categorization of loans by quality and composition. This definition, in our opinion, is a positive approach to revealing the essence of the credit portfolio. The positive aspect is that they emphasize the need to categorize loans by their qualitative composition, taking into account certain factors.

Another group of foreign economists, K.J. Bralton and D. McNaughton, believe that a commercial bank credit line is a classification of loans according to certain characteristics. This definition is based on the classification of a credit line according to specific forms and characteristics of the loan.

The importance of marketing in supporting a personalized approach to selling products depends on the parameters that determine consumer satisfaction and perception of services [4]. It can be seen that even with the marketing services of many international banks, there is no easy way to sell banking products. Because standardization is always subject to different regulatory frameworks, cultures, languages, and social concepts.

Of course, the main document in determining the client's creditworthiness is a certificate of income from work. However, in most cases, borrowers also have other official and additional sources of income that can be indicated as a source of loan repayment in the future. However, the rules for taking into account such income are determined independently by banks. Therefore, if there are additional sources of income, potential borrowers should consult with the bank in advance about whether or not to take into account this income. Since this may be important when choosing a bank for a loan or it may be necessary to provide a third-party guarantee.

Based on the cases studied above, we believe that it is always relevant to conduct research on ways to improve the efficiency of credit line management in commercial banks of our republic.

Research methodology

This of the article theoretical and methodological basis as general economic literature and scientific articles, economist of scientists commerce in banks credit line effective management issues according to research, scientists and industry representatives with conversation , their writing and mouth opinions analysis to do, expert evaluation, processes observation, economic event and to processes systematic approach, author experiences with comparative analysis transfer through relevant in directions conclusion, suggestion and recommendations given. The subject to learn in the process general economic methods with one in line information systematize according to special approaches , that is comparison, theoretical and practical materials concentration and systematic analysis such as methods used.

Analysis and results

In accordance with the Resolution of the Board of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 24/5 dated September 28, 2019, in accordance with the Regulation "On Regulation of the Debt Burden of Borrowers", the lender has the right to use the following supporting documents and information when determining the borrower's average monthly income:

- Salary information confirmed by the employer;
- information on the amount of pension;
- about citizens' accumulated pension contributions ;

- information about the borrower's income received in bank accounts;
- information on taxes paid;
- Information confirming other regular income, such as interest, dividends, property rental, etc.

That is, according to the law, when applying for a loan, the borrower can show the bank any official income confirmed by relevant documents. These are mainly taxable income of an individual. A person may not have an official job, receive income from other sources and pay taxes on them.

Indeed, in cases where a person does not have an official job, but has official income, he can get a loan from a bank. However, unfortunately, in practice this is not the case, all banks have a requirement for an official place of work. The following table 1 was compiled by the author.

In this regard, on April 5, 2023, at a videoconference meeting held by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to discuss the "Mortgage Program for 2023", it was noted that starting from May 1, 2023, the population with insufficient official income will be able to obtain a mortgage loan, and when determining their solvency, bank card turnover, rent, utility bills and other expenses will also be taken into account.

Table 1 below provides information on which sources of income are taken into account by banks when granting a loan or are not taken into account at all. That is, the sources of income of individuals that are considered as grounds for granting a loan and those that are not are listed. Pension payments are social benefits received by the client upon reaching a certain age (status) and social status. The borrower confirms this on the basis of an extract from his pension account.

Table 1. Physical to individuals retail loans in separation into account removable and types of income that are not taken into account¹

No.	Banks by into account removable income	Accounted by banks unearned income
1.	Salary – fixed part (salary, monthly bonuses) (for example, category for, experience for and others))	Precious from papers income received
2.	Salary - variable part (rewards and bonuses, commission income received as a result of implementing certain plans and/or achieving certain results)	One disposable insurance payments
3.	Vacation pay	Buying and selling currency, securities, commodities, movable and immovable property, etc. revenues from operations
4.	Dividends	Winnings and prizes from lotteries, gambling
5.	Stable insurance payments income in the form of	Fines and penalties received
6.	Rent real estate income from giving	Bonus payments (basic and additional) outside the workplace)
7.	Pension payments	State benefits (except for temporary disability benefits)
8.	Other income	Alimony
9.		Scholarships from educational institutions
10.		Rewards for donors
11.		One-time annual bonuses

¹ Source: Compiled by the author based on information from the official website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Dividends are the income received by a client who is a shareholder (participant) of a legal entity from the distribution of the profits of a legal entity according to their shares in the authorized capital of this organization. The following documents are provided to confirm that the client receiving the loan has received dividends:

- minutes of the meeting of participants of a legal entity on the payment of dividends;
- a document confirming that tax has been paid on income in the form of dividends.

In most cases, dividend income is included in the client's total income if the borrower has received such payments for at least one year and there is a possibility of receiving such income in the future. Income in the form of stable insurance payments is a fee paid using an insurance payment system by concluding a contract between the client and the insurance company for survival to a certain age.

Real estate rental income is income that a client receives from renting out property that they own. The following documents may be required to confirm this:

- a certificate confirming the client's ownership of the property to be rented;
- a lease agreement between the current (and previous) parties;
- a bank statement confirming that the client has received rent for the last 12 months;
- Documents confirming the payment of taxes on income from renting real estate in the previous year (payment orders or other documents).

Thus, it is incorrect to consider income other than the official monthly salary from a formal job as the borrower's only source of income.

Work has been accelerated in banks to introduce a modern risk management system, and underwriting and scoring systems have been introduced to ensure the short-term review of credit applications from businesses and individuals.

According to the recommendations of experts from the International Finance Corporation, The bank's lending system was transferred from a 3-stage system to a 1-stage system. A system of making decisions on granting or rejecting a loan was now implemented in only one stage at the Head Office (in the old system there were 3 stages). As a result of the cessation of the activities of branches and regional commissions, the consideration of loan applications was significantly accelerated, the number of required documents was reduced and simplified, and the influence of the human factor in decision-making was sharply reduced. As a result, the number of employees participating in the lending process was reduced by almost 2.5 times. While in the previous system the number of employees participating in the consideration of loan applications was 14, in the new system the number of participants decreased to a maximum of 6.

The bank has established 3 departments (Retail Loans, Loans to Small and Medium-Sized Businesses, and Corporate Clients) with underwriters. The activities of branch and regional commissions have been suspended. From now on, loan applications will be reviewed only at the Head Office, by underwriting staff within the scope of their authority levels.

Provisional regulations, flowcharts, procedures for electronic document circulation, and a matrix clearly defining the authority of underwriters at the Head Office were developed for reviewing and making decisions on loan applications by underwriters, and clear regulations (deadlines) for reviewing applications were established.

In the underwriting system, decisions on small loans (up to 3 billion soums) are made independently by a group of underwriters without the intervention of "officials" who work directly with the client, and loan documents are processed within 2 hours, depending on the purpose and amount of the loan.

It is processed within 24 hours. When considering loan applications from individuals, the bank uses a number of electronic databases Quick loan disbursement was organized with just an application and passport.

we will consider what factors influence the bank's negative decision. The following 2 tables were compiled by the author.

Table 2. Physical to individuals credit in separation refusal to grow reasons²

No.	Reasons
1.	The bank credit to the policy and requirements suitable not.
2.	Credit history bad to be or there is not .
3.	Low profitability or income confirmation possibility absence.
4.	Applicant high debt load
5.	Physical person's short work period or work internship there is not.
6.	Credit for of the pledge absence or pledge from insurance refusal
7.	Counterfeit and lie information presented to be
8.	The bank scoring from the system designated from demand low to score.
9.	Conviction and credit not to give basis divider of offenses existence
10.	Banks black on the list to be
11.	Suspicious or illegal behavior.

Often, the reason for banks' refusal to provide loans to individuals is the clients themselves, that is, they are doing something wrong. However, in some cases, banks may also refuse to provide credit, checking the client based on their own requirements. One of the reasons for such a refusal is non-compliance with the bank's credit policy and requirements

Each bank allocates loans to its customers based on its own credit policy and requirements. Often, people apply for a loan without paying attention to the terms of the loan. As a result, the loan conditions do not suit them, which inevitably leads to the loan not being granted. Each bank imposes certain requirements on borrowers based on its own credit policy. For example, the minimum and maximum age of the borrower, the absence of citizenship of the Republic of Uzbekistan or being a citizen of another country, etc.

The bank employee does not even have to explain to the applicant the reasons for rejecting his loan application. Moreover, unlike a client with a bad credit history, a client's application that does not meet the bank's requirements is immediately rejected by the system and is not even checked.

When considering a loan application, a bank employee or the bank's automated system sends a request to the credit bureau "Credit Information and Analysis Center". This credit bureau is an organization that collects information on the loans and some other obligations of bank clients, analyzes the financial activities of credit information subjects, provides credit information to users, calculates credit scores, and provides other services.

- The following information is sent to the credit bureau:
- existing loans and outstanding debts;
- information about debts from other microcredit organizations;
- information about installment payments in retail stores;
- Information about collateral and guarantees provided by the client (co-borrower).

If the applicant has overdue debts, the bank employee will consider the applicant unreliable and may refuse to grant the client a loan.

² Source: Compiled by the author based on information from the official website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

If the borrower has a low income or cannot confirm the legitimacy of his income, that is, cannot provide a confirmed annual salary, the borrower will still be refused a loan. Moreover, in this case, not only the amount of salary and other income is taken into account, but also how much of it is spent on paying the monthly loan payment. That is, bank specialists make calculations taking into account the borrower's income and expenses, and only official income is taken into account. So, if the client's income is not official or he cannot confirm his income, the bank may refuse to provide him with a loan.

When making a decision to grant a loan, banks always assess the borrower's ability to make future payments. This is the applicant's debt burden. The bank calculates the ratio of the borrower's average monthly payment on all loans to the borrower's average monthly income. That is, all payments on loans should not exceed 50-70 percent of income.

The calculations take into account the following:

- the amount of the borrower's official income, that is, exactly official and confirmed;
- monthly payments on all loans from other banks;
- the borrower's payment on the new loan, etc.

One of the reasons why an applicant's loan is not approved is the individual's short work period or lack of work experience. Banks logically believe that the longer a person works in one place, the more responsible he is, which means that the borrower will be able to repay the loan regularly. Therefore, banks pay attention to the minimum length of service established at the last place of work.

When a borrower provides collateral for a loan, collateral insurance is a mandatory requirement. In most cases, banks offer insurance services from insurance companies they cooperate with. This is convenient for both the bank and the client. However, in some cases, clients do not want the offered insurance. This can also lead to a negative decision on the loan application.

Various types of incorrect information provided to the bank may be considered false information:

- Incorrect personal information in the application;
- providing incorrect information provided for communication;
- Inconsistency between the information on the submitted income and the actual income, and other circumstances. If the applicant's place of work seems suspicious to the bank and there is no such official office, the bank may decide to refuse the loan.

In order to further accelerate the processing of loan applications, simplify documents, and further reduce the impact of the human factor, a number of works are being carried out to obtain information from electronic databases, analyze it, and automate decision-making, as well as effectively use the capabilities of "big data" and artificial intelligence. As a result, decisions will be made in the bank when granting loans to individuals through a 100% automated system.

As a result of the transformation of the banking system of Uzbekistan, the banking structure was revised, and as a result of optimizing the bank's service processes and transferring lending processes to single-tier lending through underwriters:

- The share of employees working with clients was increased from 16-20 percent to 50 percent (in international banking practice, this figure is 90 percent);
- The part of the bank building used for customer service was 30-40 percent, which was increased to 55 percent (in international banking practice, this figure is 80-90 percent);
- The average number of loans per employee per month was 10, and has now been increased to 22 (in international banking practice, this figure is 33);
- As a result of creating greater convenience for customers and enabling customers to perform banking services without visiting the bank, the share of remote banking users has increased

from 11 percent to 50 percent (in international banking practice, this figure is 85 percent).

To create convenience for customers and increase the popularity of banking services, banks have implemented customer service optimization (transition from the old system to the new system). As a result, the credit department, cash department, accounting department, cash desk and plastic card departments no longer provide separate services, but the front-office employees directly provide universal services. That is, the front-office employee provides services to the client and submits documents related to all services performed to the back-office.

As a result, the transition to a front-office and back-office system in customer service has led to improved customer-bank relations. All branches, mini-banks and banking service centers provide all types of services to individuals and legal entities as points of sale.

Retail lending services are also being implemented on-site. Lending processes have been simplified, an online lending service system has been developed that allows customers to receive loans without any documents, and the ability to service them without having to visit the bank.

In addition, today, banking service centers provide all banking services for individuals and legal entities, namely payments, money transfers, credit issuance, opening plastic cards, cash withdrawals and deposits. These centers are being established in crowded and convenient places. As of January 1, 2023, 1,543 banking service centers and minibanks of commercial banks and 2,974 24/7 branches are operating.

The majority of bank clients are individuals, and their number is increasing from year to year. Traditional methods of providing them with fast and high-quality offline services are associated with high costs for today's banks. In such conditions, the need for remote organization of automated and digitalized modern banking services for a large number of people is increasing, which encourages banks to widely use digital technologies, integrate their databases with the databases of relevant state bodies and other organizations. As a result, a strong competitive environment is created in banks. That is, banks need to introduce new digital services that meet the needs of their clients, be the first to introduce innovative banking services, and introduce services based on FinTech and automated systems. Based on the above, the following conclusions were drawn in the process of analyzing the ways to develop retail banking services in the context of digital transformation:

- Banks in Uzbekistan should focus on attracting advanced digital technologies to transform their operations in line with foreign experience and standards, establishing partnerships with international financial institutions or foreign FinTech companies;
- It is necessary to reduce banking costs through the digitization and automation of retail banking services based on modern financial technologies, and to establish a system that provides fast, high-quality, and transparent service to customers;
- Unless traditional banks digitize and automate their operations based on financial technologies, they will lose out in competition with digital banks that operate at lower costs;
- increase the attractiveness of loan products and types offered by banks to individuals and fully explain their terms to the population. In particular, it is necessary to provide information about the interest rate of the loan, its repayment procedure and schedule;
- Retail lending practices should be implemented with full use of artificial intelligence-based assessment models. Today, the retail lending process is widely using a scoring system for assessing a client's creditworthiness. Organizing scoring based on artificial intelligence will reduce the human factor and provide customers with quick loans;
- It is necessary to take measures to increase the financial literacy of potential customers and employees so that both bank employees and customers are fully familiar with the use of retail banking services based on modern financial technologies and innovative banking technologies;
- In the economic literature, lending to individuals is mainly used with two terms, expressed by

the concepts of “consumer credit” and “retail lending”. Although these concepts have common aspects, some economists have used these concepts as synonyms, while others have explained them differently. This creates scientific uncertainty in assessing the practices of commercial banks in granting loans to individuals.

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